

Solid phase selective oxidation of β -sitosterol and 4 β -hydroxy cholesterol by *N*-bromosuccinimide – A green approach

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Manuscript received online 25 February 2014, accepted 08 July 2014

Abstract : Selective aromatization of A-ring of β -sitosterol was achieved by using *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) through simple one-pot solid phase synthesis. Application of the same protocol on 4 β -hydroxycholesterol leads to the formation of 3-keto-4 β ,5 α ,6 β -trihydroxycholesterol. Both the products were characterised by full spectral data (NMR, IR, UV, Mass, etc.). Thus, NBS in solid phase furnished selective oxidation of the above mentioned two steroids.

Keywords : Methyl-19-norstigmast-1,3,5(10)-triene, 3-keto-4 β ,5 α ,6 β -trihydroxy cholesterol, solid phase.

Introduction

Steroids are one of the most important classes of compounds both in terms of chemical and biological considerations and so are their derivatives. Among them, oxidized steroids have a special place in this field because of their diverse properties as well as immense applications in biology^{1,2}. During the derivatization, different reagents were used by different scientific groups. *N*-Bromosuccinimide (NBS) is one such important transforming protocol which was used to carry out bromination as well as oxidation of steroids. Bromination by NBS was reported for enol acetates of 3-keto steroids at C2 or C4³, 3 β -acetoxy-5-androsten-17-one at C5⁴ and 17,20-enol acetate of pregnenolone at C17⁵. Besides, NBS was found to be a good dehydrogenating agent for the enol acetate of 20-keto steroid producing C16-C17 double bond⁶ and for Δ^7 -cholesteryl benzoate, producing $\Delta^{7,9(11)}$ diene⁷. Fieser and Rajagopalan reported the formation of cholic acid from deoxycholic acid etherate by using NBS in acetic acid-water. NBS also oxidized methyl etiocholate to the 7-keto derivative and desoxycholic acid to diketo acid⁸⁻¹¹. Similarly, NBS with methyl-3 α -acetoxy $\Delta^{7,9(11)}$ -choladienate in t-BuOH-dil. H₂SO₄ at 0 °C furnished methyl-3 α -acetoxy-7-keto- $\Delta^{9(11)}$ -cholenate, methyl-3 α -acetoxy-11-keto- Δ^8 -cholenate and methyl-3 α -acetoxy-11- α -hydroxy-7-keto- Δ^8 -cholenate¹². NBS was also found to be effective in forming cholestan-3 β ,5 α -diol-6-one ei-

ther from cholesterol or from cholestan-3 β ,5 α ,6 β -triol or from cholesterol α -oxide in aqueous acetone, though monobromo- and dibromo-derivatives were also formed in poor amounts from the last substrate. Cholesteryl α -oxide acetate was also converted to the corresponding 6-keto compound by *N*-bromosuccinimide¹³. After reflux with *N*-bromosuccinimide in carbon tetrachloride, cholesteryl acetate produced a solid primarily assumed to be 3 β -acetoxy- Δ^5 -cholestene-4 β ,7 α -diol which was later identified as 4 β -acetoxy- Δ^5 -cholestene-3 β ,7 α -diol by Jailer and his coworkers^{14,15}.

NBS in a number of organic solvents was also employed to convert 17 α -hydroxy-21-acyloxy-4-pregnene-3,11,20-trione into 11 β ,17 α -dihydroxy-21-acyloxy-4-pregnene-3,20-diones¹⁶. Besides bromination, NBS in CHCl₃ was used to hydrolyze 3-methoxymethyl ether-2-trimethylsilyl derivative of oestradiol to form 2-bromo oestradiol¹⁷. Similarly 5 α -bromocholestane-3 β ,6 β -diol 3-acetate was achieved from cholesteryl acetate by NBS¹⁸. NBS could also play the role of a catalyst for the esterification of tertiary alcohols of cyproterone (CYP) and medroxyprogesterone (MGP) to produce 6-chloro-17-hydroxy-1 α ,2 α -methylene-4,6-pregnadien-3,20-dione 17 α -acetate and 17 α -hydroxy-6 α -methylpregn-4-ene-3,20-dione acetate, respectively¹⁹.

Hanson and Organ have reported a steroidal aromatization reaction which includes a transformation of cho-

lesterol into A-ring aromatized product 4-methyl-19-norcholesta-1,3,5(10)-triene on treatment with 1,3-dibromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin^{20–22}. But they were unable to isolate the compound in its pure form^{14,15}. They reported NBS as a poorer alternative to hydantoin whereas our laboratory has reported the selective aromatization of A-ring of cholesterol in solid phase by using NBS²³. In continuation to this, herein we report the action of NBS in solid phase, on two specific steroids, one having one hydroxyl group and another possessing two hydroxyl groups in their skeleton. The reactions (Schemes 1 and 2) furnished two different kinds of products in each case, though both the reactants bear the steroidal skeleton. One of the products was identical to that obtained by the dehydrohalogenation of 3 β -chloro-5 α -bromo-5 α -stigmastan-6 β -ol, as was performed by Akhrem *et al.*²⁴.

Results and discussion

A mixture of β -sitosterol, **1** (0.41 g, 1.0 mmol) and NBS (0.42 g, 5.0 mmol) in activated silica furnished a selective aromatic product 1-methyl-19-norstigmast-1,3,5(10)-triene, **2** (Scheme 1). Compound **2** appeared as pale yellow gum (10%, 0.04 g, 0.1 mmol) with characteristic odour. The product is actually identical with that obtained by Akhrem *et al.*²⁴.

Scheme 1. One-pot synthesis of 1-methyl-19-norstigmast-1,3,5(10)-triene.

In another reaction, 4 β -hydroxy cholesterol, **3** (0.40 g, 1.0 mmol) and NBS (0.42 g, 5.0 mmol) in activated silica produced a trihydroxy keto compound, **4** (Scheme 2). Compound **4** was isolated as white solid product (30%,

Scheme 2. One-pot synthesis of 3-keto-4 β ,5 α ,6 β -trihydroxy cholesterol.

0.13 g, 0.3 mmol). The isolated single product was characterized with the help of full spectroscopic analysis. Most possibly the allylic alcoholic group has a significant role to give rise to double bond hydroxylation because, it was not achieved from β -sitosterol. Selective oxidation of 1,2-diols with NBS is well established and combining the previous results with our experiment on 4 β -hydroxycholesterol, it can be stated that 1,2-diols are oxidized to α -hydroxy ketones and the hydroxy group (of the diol) adjacent to a $-\text{CH}_2$ group gets oxidized.

Products characterization :

Compound 2 :

IR (neat) ($\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 721 (arom. H), 1377 (CH_3 def.), 2922 (arom. H str.); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.68 (3H, s), 0.82 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 0.85 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.25 (3H, s), 2.21 (3H, s), 6.99 (1H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 7.07 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 7.19 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 11.9, 18.6, 18.8, 19.1 and 19.8 (5CH_3), 23.1 (CH_2), 23.9 (CH_3), 23.9, 26.1, 27.2, 27.8 and 28.3 (5CH_2), 29.2 (CH), 29.7 (CH), 33.9 (CH_2), 36.2 (CH), 37.9 (CH_2), 40.1 (CH_2), 42.7 (C), 44.5, 45.9, 55.7, 56.3, 123.1, 125.2 and 127.2 (7CH), 135.3, 136.3 and 140.7 (3C).

Compound 4 :

IR (KBr) ($\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 3500 (intramolecular H-bond), 3224 (intermolecular H-bond), 1718 (C=O), 1456 (CH_3 , CH_2 def.), 1382 (C- CH_3 def.), 1051–1253, (C-O str.), 713–833; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 0.68 (3H, s), 0.86 (3H, d, J 6.3 Hz), 0.91 (d, J 6.3 Hz), 1.21 (3H, s), 1.42 (3H, s), 2.30–2.44 (1H, m), 5.35 (1H, t, J 9.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 12.1, 18.6 and 19.0 (3CH_3), 21.5 (CH_2), 22.5 and 22.8 (2CH_3), 23.7 and 23.9 (CH_2), 28.0 (CH), 28.1 (CH_2), 30.1 (CH), 30.5, 32.5 and 32.6 (3CH_2), 35.7 (CH), 36.1, 39.4 and 39.6 (3CH_2), 42.6 and 43.8 (2C), 46.2, 55.5, 56.1, 70.4, 71.5

Ghosh *et al.* : Solid phase selective oxidation of β -sitosterol and 4β -hydroxy cholesterol by *N*-bromosuccinimide *etc.*

and 78.7 (6CH), 210.7 (C=O); DART-MS, *m/z* (%) : 400, 399 (100%), 398, 397.

Experimental

Infrared spectrum was measured in Shimadzu FTIR 8300 spectrometer either in neat (for compound **2**) or in KBr (for compound **4**), purchased from Merck. NMR spectra were recorded on a 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometer with CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal reference; chemical shifts are expressed as δ ppm. Mass spectrum was measured on a JEOL-AccuTOF JMS-T100LC Mass spectrometer. Analytical-TLC was performed with silica gel plates using silica gel G for thin layer chromatography (Thomas Baker).

Procedure for the preparation of 2 from β -sitosterol : Silica gel (60–120 mesh, 1.0 g) was activated (150 °C/1 mm Hg, 1 h) and mixed with β -sitosterol (0.41 g, 1.0 mmol) and *N*-bromosuccinimide (recrystallized from hot water to have white crystals, 0.42 g, 5.0 mmol) taking in a dry mortar. The mixture was then pasted well to dust by a pestle, transferred to a round bottom flask and was kept in stirring for 72 h. Next, chloroform (50 mL) was poured, filtered and the filtrate was washed with water (3 \times 30 mL) and dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was purified by column chromatography using petroleum ether as the eluent. Compound **2** appeared as a pale yellow gum (10% yield) with characteristic odour.

Procedure for the preparation of 4 from 4β -hydroxy cholesterol : First, 4β -hydroxy cholesterol was obtained directly from cholesterol using selenium dioxide²⁵. Compound **4** was then prepared from 4β -hydroxy cholesterol (0.40 g, 1 mmol) using NBS (0.42 g, 5 mmol) following the same method as mentioned above for compound **2**.

Conclusion

In summary, we have accomplished the syntheses of A-ring aromatized β -sitosterol and 3-keto- $4\beta,5\alpha,6\beta$ -tri-hydroxy cholesterol using a very simple, solvent-free and non-hazardous method. The methodology worked as a cost effective and environmentally benign transforming protocol to furnish the steroidal oxidation products selectively.

References

1. Z. Xinhua, Y. Shaoyu, L. Huiqin, R. Shihong, Z. Baofeng and M. Xiaoshuo, *Zhongguo Yaowu Huaxue Zazhi*, 1995, **5**, 101.
2. A. Honda, T. Yoshida, N. Tanaka, Y. Matsuzaki, B. He, J. Shoda and T. Osuga, *J. Gastroenterol.*, 1995, **30**, 651.
3. M. Rubin and B. H. Armbrrecht, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3513.
4. S-J. Zhang, F. Xu and W-X. Hu, *J. Chem. Crystallogr.*, 2010, **40**, 997.
5. F. K. Yoshimoto, M. C. Desilets and R. J. Auchus, *J. Steroid Biochem.*, 2012, **128**, 38.
6. C. Djerassi and C. R. Scholz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, **14**, 660.
7. L. F. Fieser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5007.
8. L. Fieser and S. Rajagopalan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **72**, 3935.
9. A. Lardon, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1947, **30**, 597.
10. H. Reich and T. Reichstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1943, **26**, 562.
11. L. H. Sarett, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1165.
12. L. Fieser, W. P. Schneider and W-Y. Huayng, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 124.
13. L. Fieser and S. Rajagopalan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **72**, 3938.
14. S. Lieberman and D. K. Fukushima, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5211.
15. R. W. Jailer, D. K. Fukushima and S. M. Lieberman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5220.
16. W. P. Schneider and M. Kalamazoo, US Patent, 1956, June 19, 2, 751, 402.
17. A. B. Turner, *Nat. Prod. Rep.*, 1989, **6**, 539.
18. M. Stefanovic, A. Jokic and M. L. Mihailovic, *Glasnik Hemijskog Drustva Beograd*, 1966, **31**, 139.
19. Z. Rezaei, S. Khabnadideh, M. M. Zarshenas and M. R. Jafari, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2007, **276**, 57.
20. J. R. Hanson and T. D. Organ, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 513
21. J. R. Hanson and T. D. Organ, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 1313.
22. J. R. Hanson and T. D. Organ, *J. Chem. Soc. (D)*, 1971, 1119.
23. P. Ghosh, J. Das and A. Sarkar, *Green Chem. Lett. Rev.*, 2012, **5**, 173.
24. A. A. Akhrem, V. A. Khripach, Zh. N. Kashkan and N. V. Kovganko, *Zhurnal Organicheskoi Khimii*, 1989, **25**, 441.
25. P. Ghosh, J. Das, A. Sarkar, S. W. Ng and E. R. T. Tiekink, *Tetrahedron*, 2012, **68**, 6485.

